

Magic as a Phenomenological Tool for Designing Technology

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Abstract

Magic has traditionally been aligned with religious practice rather than with science and the arts, but design, with its strong focus on the social, symbolic and ritual value of objects has much to learn from an understanding of the mechanisms of magic. Magic may be seen as the performance of particular rites by a magician, and it follows that anyone who performs these rites is a magician. The experience of interacting with the type of objects and services we encounter in everyday life may be taken, in part, and mapped against very similar mechanisms to those of a magician. This observation is particularly acute in the case of digital, and wireless devices, where the promise of the ‘black-box’ remains extremely powerful. The sophistication and integration of these devices makes it very easy for the user to exercise control, or power at a distance; one of the strongest defining characteristics of the magician.

If our user becomes a magician, how can the designer increase the effect to make the power stronger? The authors attempt to answer this question through the introduction of a framework that will help designers navigate the various elements that constitute a magical engagement with products or services. The first part of this employs the metaphor of hardware and software in relation to objects and rites. This explores the notion that an object (hardware) might be rendered more powerful when our user (magician) invokes particular rites. These might be in the form of branding, packaging, software, interface etc. but in each case it is his power that renders their power effective.

The research unfolds a phenomenology of magical objects, providing a potentially useful entry-point and lens for the design of new products. The authors also present a matrix of experiential relations that pertain to the relationship between ‘the magical’, ‘the artefact-actor’, and ‘the human-actor’. A series of experimental workshops have helped the authors in the development of a framework through which these issues might be better understood and implemented in mainstream design processes.

Keywords: Magic, Technology, Phenomenology, Experience, Showmanship

Introduction

Magic as an encompassing worldview and cultural norm has been effectively combated or restrained by organized religion, industry and modernity, in almost every corner of the world. Yet it seems as if, in conjunction with the widespread of microelectronic information and communication devices, magical beliefs, perceptions and the subsequent behaviours and languaging of magic are forging a reappearance on the cultural and social stage of twenty first century life. Indeed, technological paradigms such as ‘augmented reality’ and ‘ubiquitous computing’ throw into sharp relief the potential for animating whole categories of artefacts that were once purely reactive and mechanical. This embedding of computing and information power into the fabric of everyday existence has the potential for incubating new experiential and behavioural norms. As George Dyson puts it, “everywhere we look things are turning out to be more intelligent and more alive than they once seemed.” (Dyson, 1997)

We participate fully in this dramatically changing milieu of devices. The previous arguments from the canon of modernity which characterise the creep of technology into everyday life as “disenchanted” and “dehumanising” (Weber, 1958) are countered by contemporary theorists such as Lash and Knorr Cetina, who instead promote the idea that human nature is adaptable enough to participate and survive, though the consequences are emergent. As Lash states, “I cannot achieve sociality apart from my machine interface. I cannot achieve sociality in the absence of technological systems, apart from my interface with communication and transportation machines” (Lash, 2001). As products from the perspectives of modernity and technoscience, the advance of artefacts capable of enacting logic and simulating or conducting communication between and with humans should have had further sobering and becalming effect. From within the perspective of modernism, the reverse now seems to be becoming the case. “Every advance in technical rationality today is surpassed by a decline in common sense and a growing irrationality, the signs of which are everywhere”.(Stivers, 2001) Such signs being a diversity of beliefs, behaviours, and a growing disconnect between the products of modern technology and the cultural forms that brought it about.

Discussions or dialogues that attempt to involve the concept of magic are beset by the problem of lacking a common or principle definition of the word and concept in question. In this study we refer to the eminent anthropologist Marcel Mauss and his observation that although the actions, aims and objects of magic differ widely – “they share one feature in that their immediate and essential effect is to modify a given state. The magician, therefore, knows full well that his magic is consequently the same. He is always conscious that magic is the art of changing – the *Maya* as the Hindus call it.” (Mauss, 2001)

While the definition of magic as ‘the art of changing’ seems too prosaic, too everyday for what feels like a special and spectacular word, we must attempt to engage with it without the cultural filters and assumptions that generate preconceptions and instead look at where it lives, what it does, what it’s effects are, and ultimately, how can design engage with this phenomenon purposefully and with clarity. As the interface design pioneer Bruce Tognazzini states, with regard to magicians, as designers “we have much to learn from them”. (Tognazzini, 1993)

Imaginative Participants and Elusive Objects

Contrary to popular opinion, when Arthur C. Clarke (1973) wrote the famous phrase (his third law) , that “any sufficiently advanced technology is indistinguishable from magic” , he was commenting on the nature of predicting the future and how imagination was a critical ingredient, as opposed to the actual magicality of new technologies from the laboratory. However, in an era where devices are becoming increasingly minituarised and complex, the popular intuition is holding more validity. The important point here is that Clarke’s original intent behind the statement still resonates, in that imagination is required for consumers to overcome the limitations of everyday knowledge in the face of an landscape of devices whose characteristics are an ever accelerating dematerialisation and are becoming increasingly responsive and ‘intelligent’.

Historically, the elaboration of science and technology has succeeded best when the popular imagination has been invited to engage with the spectacle of entertaining public

lectures and magic shows. “Nineteenth-century popular science not only inherited it’s instruments from natural magic but also a tradition of public performance that subordinated the visual articulation of instruction and amusement to the intensification of aesthetic effect. Therein lay the secret to turning science into entertainment.” (Pierson, 2002) It is the authors proposition that design can utilise magic to turn consumers into ‘prosumers’ or at least participants in the construction of technologically mediated meaning, as enhancing the process of ‘becoming’ in a complex world. Design as supporting that process of a magically enriched ‘becoming’ through the provision of appropriate props, tools, and routines (or rituals).

Technology makes it’s presence felt in the market and through marketing. As Bruce Sterling reminds us, technological effects and it’s corollary, effective intervention, occur in social relations and through the performance of those relations through technology. “Effective intervention takes place not in the human, not in the object, but in the realm of the technosocial.” (Sterling, 2005). It is therefore interesting to note that much of design research on the ethics and experiences of technological design is centered on the artefact and the design. The artefact is a site of “production” and performance.

Writing on sociology of technology, Knorr Cetina echoes Sterling, “. . . authors pay scant attention to the nature of knowledge processes and knowledge cultures, and they tend to see knowledge as an intellectual or technological product rather than as a production context in its own right (Knorr Cetina, 1999).

This location of the production of meaning and of politics leaves research and analysis initially with the difficulty of identifying the object of it’s attention. People cannot speak easily or sensibly of their relations *through* things, particularly if the dimensions under enquiry are potentially outside the conventions of what it is to be rational and of the mainstream culture or production and consumption.

Writing on the industry and culture of special effects in film, Michelle Pierson illuminates the active role played by enculturated and experienced cinema-goers. “Within

a discourse of effects connoisseurship, the experience of wonder depends on knowing enough to be surprised. Wonder, in this sense, is taking delight in having one's expectations met. Or, to turn this proposition around, connoisseurship expresses desire for the experience of wonder as a demand." (Pierson, 2002) While not deflecting the immediate impasse of the invisible object of our research, Pierson is suggesting that consumers are active participants in the 'spectacular', which is similar to how magic works on stage and in the everyday. You have to participate to be entertained and to derive meaning from the experience.

Rather than interrogate subjects as to their fetishisation of technology or their magically oriented imaginations in connection with devices and gizmos, this research has conducted itself through the methodology of phenomenology in order to uncover what is otherwise elusive to talk about. Lash expresses the potential of this method when he writes, "phenomenological inquiry makes sense of the world less through "intellection", but rather through what Husserl and Bergson called "intuition". We have knowledge, not through the abstraction of judgment, but through the immediacy of experience. Intuition is more bodily and organic than intellection; experience more life-like (Erlebnis in German) than judgment." (Lash, 2001) It is at this level of intuition, of pre-rationality that we anticipate finding evidence of magic in twenty-first century human-device relationships.

Design as Enabling 'Showmanship'

The application of magic affords a process of *transformation* in one form or another. This might be the transmutation from one material into another, the translation from one place to another. This links it very closely to ideas of manufacture and commerce; the monetary gain through changing one thing into another. The judicious application of land, labour and capital turns raw material into something to be traded at a price. In an age of over-abundance, mass-communication and market freedom, the end-product needs to squeeze as much out of the process as possible in order to turn a profit. This is where a touch of magic comes in handy. Judith Williamson in her book 'Decoding

Advertisements,' tells us that *'Magic is the production of results disproportionate to the effort put in (a transformation of power - or of impotence into power).*'ⁱ but also that *'all consumer products offer magic, and all advertisements are spells.'*ⁱⁱ Design and marketing are clearly central to this transformation, and only in performing this magic are they useful to the system. Our magician is in his element as he describes the benefits of his patent cure to an enthralled audience, who gasp when his stooge makes a miraculous recovery. As the audience for these tricks becomes more and more sophisticated, so, too do the performers, but it reaches a limit at which each knows as much as each other. In their book, *The Experience Economy*, Joseph Pine and James Gilmore argue that this is the point at which a mature market gives way to a more efficient model. In this case, it becomes related to experiences, rather than objects and the 'thing' being consumed is the memory of the experience. In many cases these are unscrupulously augmented through the sale of signifiers of the experience, souvenirsⁱⁱⁱ. Whether glossy programmes, replica football shirts or Star Wars toys, these have long benefited from their status as the perfect product: they have a captive market at mass events, they can be marketed at gigantic mark-up, and they can be altered ad-infinitum to generate repeat sales. As the shift towards an economy based on experience takes place, it will have to be the experience itself that makes the money, not the merchandise.

In terms of the magician, our performer has now given up trying to sell us his snake oil or magic beans, he has ditched the product and is putting on a show for us. He even invites us up on stage to pick a card or help cut the assistant in half. At some point, though, we grow tired of the monotony of the tricks being performed. This is when we take to the stage ourselves. Rather than being passive observers, we rise to the challenge of performance ourselves. In some areas of design practice, this phenomenon can be observed. Taking the notion that products are 'props' for a lived experience, there are starting to emerge from some schools and consultancies props that challenge the user, rather than pander to stereotypical, and commonly aspired to, lifestyles. The work of Tony Dunne, Fiona Raby and Noam Toran, for instance, is hard to relate to popular notions of commercial design. Dunne and Raby suggest the link between their work and the genre of film noir.^{iv} Toran has gone as far as actually making the films, casting

himself in the role of the protagonist and using of props he has designed along the way. All this work has had its imitators, and is becoming common currency in design criticism. There is nothing much that mirrors this in the marketplace however. Perhaps the idea of these products is too much. Certainly they don't work as one would expect. They are not 'products' at all in the normal sense that you go out and buy them, take them home and 'use' them. They are objects that take on an identity of their own and demand that the user interpret them. In terms of 'use' value, they are more closely related to art, but they *look* like furniture.

Perhaps this is the realm in which we are beginning to witness a maturing of the economic value of these things – towards *transformation*. In the eyes of Pine and Gilmore, this manifests itself in educational and 'improving' experiences, such as taking a class in martial arts, visiting a museum, or even eating Benecol (a cholesterol-reducing spread). In these cases, they argue, the '*customer becomes the product*.'^v In this sense, the objects created by Dunne and Raby could be seen to fit the mould. The transformation, however, rather than being a commonly recognised goal, is toward an existentialist consideration and re-negotiation of the *use* of these objects. At the same time, the user is learning new modes of interaction with their surroundings, and, potentially, learning not to take them for granted. This is not an isolated practice. It seems to link with the prevalence of an ad-hoc approach to design that has gained popularity in recent years, particularly amongst emerging young designers. This reflects an increasing dissatisfaction with prevalent models of design which, despite a new-found freedom in terms of form, material and technology, do little to question or challenge the notion that serial consumption is good. In that sense, truly novel forms of design practice tend to emerge from outside conventions of the discipline.

An initial Phenomenology of Magic in Designed Devices

An initial analysis of existing contemporary technological devices and 'gizmos' was conducted in both United Kingdom and New Zealand, of over one hundred and fifty artefacts, a selection of which are illustrated in fig.1 . These two phenomenological

analyses of technological devices raised a variety of variant and invariant forms that, upon interpretation, were contributing factors to either or both the performer and the audience.

After contrasting the two studies, the eight factors that were agreed upon have been grouped under four basic headings.

1) **Presence:**

(dis)appearance/(in)visibility

Appearance and disappearance refer here to the capacity of the device being manipulated by the performer to enter and exit the sensible field of the spectator. Visibility and invisibility on the other hand, refer to the persistence of the artefact and its field of effect in the sensible field of the audience.

2) **Control**

responsiveness to input / unique input

Control here is not about the ability to exert dominion over the physical artefact itself, rather the manner in which control over the device's function, capacity or power is negotiated by the performer. Therefore, a device's responsiveness to a users input can fall either side of 'normal' responsiveness, i.e; being predictive or anticipatory on the one hand, and responding in a truculent or disobedient manner on the other.

3) **Causation**

action over time and distance / control of 3rd objects

Action over distance is a familiar category of when discussing magical or enchanting technologies as it vividly extends human agency by non-physical means. Within the scope of this project, the extension of action, or more specifically causation, is over both time and space. In a similar manner to the experience of collapsing and expanding space via the use of mobile phones and remote controls, time is also compressed or stretched out via the deployment of mediating technologies such as video recorders and answering services.

4) Communication

(in)constant / (in)comprehendability

The type of communication referred to here is the sonic, visual, and kinetic produced by both the performer and the artefact in question during a performance. Whilst most performances are accompanied by a verbal narrative or 'patter', it is particularly the non-linguistic information that interests the designer. The communication between the device and the user, and between the device or the user to the spectators.

The constancy and rhythm of the communication imparts the sense of conversationality, whether or not such a relationship is actually present. Such conversations are not in themselves necessarily entered into, rather they are the sensible features of awareness of one or more others, an alteric awareness that may or may not be welcome.

The comprehendability also contributes to the sense of an awareness and helps define the nature or character of the intelligence that is being aware. We do not necessarily need to understand the content of a communication to know that it directed, potentially, at us.

Design Experiments

Following the phenomenological analysis of contemporary technological devices, the unfolding of experiential features of 'magicality' in and through technology, the research turned toward stimulating possible magical experience through design experiment. That is to say that by stretching the designed reality of artefacts toward enabling magical performativity a set of 'phenomenological probes' could be established to begin unfolding future potential. Not so much drawing parallels between Design and Magic, but

more precisely using Design to understand more fully the new form magic may be taking in daily life, and in turn how design can actively participate in this phenomena.

In order to begin unfolding the potential for magic through design, workshops have been conducted in the United Kingdom and New Zealand with a total of 41 undergraduate and postgraduate design students. These workshops were short, concept focussed affairs which employed the four-pair framework illustrated previously as the entry point. Working with the four-pairs relationship, students were encouraged to design objects as interfaces and imbue them with properties that could enable the ‘magical’. The domains within which this phase of the work took place were fairly typical product arenas, such that departures or differences from normative practice could be easily identified, they were: ‘kitchen whiteware’ and ‘signage’. The outputs were varied in their creative range, they were all however generating novel and atypical aspects of interaction with and through technology. Several of the designs are illustrated below in fig.2 .

The designed outputs were taken to a second stage of analysis, whereby the artefacts themselves were phenomenologically described, reinforcing the four pairs of principles previously stated, and the performances that the designers enacted were recorded and analysed as participative scenarios in the manner described by Iacucci, et al. (Iacucci, Kuutti and Ranta, 2000). The method used here was a derivative of role-playing based design scenarios, supported by the adoption of appropriate personae developed from a wide variety of first-hand and online data. The difference here being that the performance

was conducted by the artefact's designer, aiming to 'perform' in front of other designers who were participating as people in social circumstances do. This method certainly claims no high position under objective criteria, it does however bring out the embodied performer in the designer, externalising a role that in itself is often 'masked' or suppressed.

Development of a Methodological Tool for Magic through Design

The data from both the second phenomenological analysis and the participative scenarios have been contrasted and combined with the writings and theoretical frameworks offered by Tognazzini (1993) and Mauss (2001). The resultant method is a set of three distinct categories of dimensions, which in turn host three principal characteristics which designers can pay consideration to when attempting to engage with and generate magical experiences and performances in and through technological devices. What follows are the three main dimensions and their constituent characteristics.

1) Perception:

Illusion - Misdirection – Continuity.

These are the basic psychological principles of performative magic, the primary techniques whereby magic is generated. This is where we find the transformative powers of magic used to deceive an audience, forcing them to witness the magical properties of mundane objects. More often than not these properties are stimulated into action, harnessed if you will, by the performer.

Illusion is the single largest factor represented here. It encompasses simulation, dissimulation, disguise, metaphor, etc. The main purpose of illusion is to make something appear what it is not, to create a new reality and set of meanings for the user, often known in design as creating the 'user-illusion' (Tognazzini, Kay). Misdirection is where the recipients attention is diverted from the 'real action' or mechanism of magic so that the secret (spectacular or banal) is not revealed. Continuity is the principle of maintaining a fluid experience for the benefit of keeping the continued attention of the audience, that the actions, words and devices employed are aligned with the everyday and with the character of the performer.

2) Magic:

Contiguity - Similarity - Opposition

Here the magic itself is the commodity. The performance and transformation is provided both for our diversion and entertainment, and contributes to a symbolic web of meanings that support or enable the act of believing the magic. This is difficult territory for industrial design as it is promoting an irrational and postmodern perspective on transparency and understanding.

According to Mauss, examining the practice of magic into which the audience and the performer are participating with the beliefs (as well as their bodies), “it is possible to extract three principal laws. They could in fact all come under the heading of laws of sympathy, if antipathy is also covered by the notion of sympathy. These are the laws of contiguity, similarity and opposition: things in contact are and remain the same – like produces like – opposites work on opposites.” (Mauss, p.79)

3) Narrative:

Expectation - Surprise – Explanation.

Here “time”, the sequential narrative or schema or delivering *or* receiving magic.

In this plane, the audience have taken over, co-opting the role of the magician in the interpretation and creation of their own narrative. This is hard to spot, but in some areas of society it is well ensconced. Pod-casting, modding (of automobiles), mass-customisation all fit this mould and see the consumer or the spectator in the place of the designer. The designer’s role has now become filled by the owner/user/performer.

Expectation refers to the anticipation the audience builds as the performances begin.

Referring again to the work by Pierson (2002), the network of consumers or users is a network of conisseurs, each holding a differing degree of prior knowledge, which in turn defines their level of expectation to be met and, possibly, exceeded.

Surprise is the moment of catalysis in magically oriented performances and experiences.

The audience is ‘won over’ or seduced, it is in effect the punch-line or moment of revealing the dissonant outcome of the, previously ordinary sequence of events. Surprise

here is a generic term that acts as a category for other sensations such as ‘shock’, ‘delight’, ‘disquiet’ and notions connected to the uncanny or to humour.

The final stage in this temporal narrative is that of explanation. Explanation occurs when the outcome of the performance that was initially dissonant or oblique to the cognitive model the spectator had held with regard to the logic of actions being performed is afterwards assimilated and a new mental model constructed, regardless of whether that model is correct or incorrect.

The three dimensional matrix presented below in figure 3 is the authors integration of the aforementioned three categories and the their individual components into a single, practical tool. It is the intention of the authors to test this more elaborate methodological device with student and professional designer’s in the near future to further determine the effectiveness of working with the concept of magic in designing technological artefacts.

Conclusion

This research is by no means exhaustive in either the range of artefacts explored and designed, or the variety of research perspectives taken up to view the phenomena through. It is an initial start into develop methods and practices by which designers may begin to consciously engage with the emerging landscape of networked, immaterial, and intelligent devices in ways which belong to a post-optimal and possibly post-rational future.

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